

Extreme Weather

A rapid deepener that produced severe damage across much of North West Scotland in November 2005. *(Image courtesy of NEODAAS/University of Dundee)*

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The Environmental Physics Group Newsletter

Spring Issue.

Welcome to the spring edition of the Environmental Physics Group's newsletter. It's lovely to have some sun after the cold and snowy winter – we don't envy those who had to endure extreme freezer-level temperatures in January!

The coming year is the 20th Anniversary of the Environmental Physics Group, so it's a great opportunity to join and meet other members at the **AGM, Environmental Physics Day and evening lecture** on cosmic rays given by Prof Sir Arnold Wolfendale of Durham University on 26th May (see pages 9-10).

If you can not make it to Environmental Physics Day, there are several other environmentally related events, for example "Physics in the Animal World" in London in November, as well as others around the country in the coming months (see pages 7-12), such as "Combustion and NO_x in the Environment" at the University of Nottingham in April. **Please note that many of the forthcoming events happen in April, so please read your newsletter before then!**

A big thank you for all of the entries that we received for the Environmental Physics Essay Competition, winners will be announced at the Environmental Physics Day in May.

In addition to the information, reports and notices of upcoming events found in this newsletter, further information can be found on our website at <http://www.iop.org/activity/groups/subject/env/>

Sally Brown and Hugh Mortimer

AGM notice

Annual General Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group

The Annual General Meeting of the Institute of Physics Environmental Physics Group will be held on **Wednesday 26 May 2010 at 5:30pm**. The meeting will be held at the Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London.

This year there are vacancies for the Officer positions of Chair and Vice-Chair/Treasurer, and for several Ordinary Committee members.

Please send nominations for the above vacancies to the Secretary, to arrive no later than twenty-eight days before the AGM. The nominations should be proposed by at least two members of the Group and should be accompanied by the written consent of the nominee.

This is your chance to become more involved with the Group and to make a difference. If you would like to know more about what might be involved, please contact the Secretary or Chair (details below) for an informal discussion.

This year's AGM will be held during the annual **Environmental Physics Day** meeting, marking the 20th anniversary of the Group. It will include a range of talks on environmental physics topics and presentations by the winners of our essay competition (see page 9). Following the AGM, there will be a lecture entitled '**Cosmic rays, climate and other matters**' by Professor Sir Arnold Wolfendale of Durham University (see page 10).

A limited number of **EPG travel grants** may be available to assist members of the EPG attending the Environmental Physics Day meeting; contact the Secretary or Chair for further details.

We look forward to seeing you at the AGM.

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Reports from previous events

The Royal Meteorological Society's 6th Biennial Summer Conference, University of Reading

This meeting was held from 29th June to 3rd July 2009 at the University of Reading and is reported by Liz Bentley, Head of Communications at the Royal Meteorological Society.

The conference was well attended with some 362 attendees registered over the four days of the conference. The conference had a strong and diverse science programme focused on the three themes of The Water Cycle, Predicting Hazards and Risk, and Ecosystems, Atmospheric Composition, Weather and Climate. There was an excellent programme of invited speakers including Professor Julia Slingo OBE, Met Office Chief Scientist

and Society President; Professor Graeme Stephens, Department of Atmospheric Science, Colorado State University; Professor Susan Solomon, Head of the Chemistry and Climate Processes Group, NOAA Chemical Sciences Division; and Professor Bob Watson, DEFRA Chief Scientific Advisor.

Each afternoon the conference ran both workshop and poster sessions related to one of the three conference themes. Reports from these workshops are on the Royal Meteorological Society's website at www.rmets.org and in the Society's journal Atmospheric Science Letters. This year's conference poster prizes (one for each theme) were kindly sponsored by Biral and were awarded to James Lloyd, John Methven, and Bethan Harris.

The conference also had an entertaining social programme including a sketch show on the 'alternative history of meteorology' by the postgraduate students of the Reading Meteorology Department, a medley of 'meteorologically-related' songs by the Met Singers, a weather themed pub quiz, and the Conference Dinner in the grounds of Mapledurham House where the Society Awards were presented.

The feedback from the conference was very positive. Those who attended enjoyed the strong invited speaker programme and welcomed the opportunity that the new format provided with more higher quality discussion time. The organising has already begun for the 2011 Conference and the Society would welcome offers from organisations to host this conference.

The Transition to Low Carbon, Winchester Discovery Centre.

This meeting was held from Friday 20th – Saturday 21st November and is reported on by Dr Nick Woodman of the University of Southampton.

The University of Southampton, Winchester Action on Climate Change and Cap and Share UK hosted a two-day workshop on 'The Transition to Low Carbon'. The workshop unusually brought together academics, sustainability practitioners and 'green' activists to look at policy as well as local-scale projects for carbon reduction.

The first day was centred on national policy, focusing particularly on environmental economics. The MPs Colin Challen and Alan Simpson talked on the Copenhagen COP and feed-in tariffs respectively. Physicist Dr Simon Roberts from Arup talked about the 'rebound effect' and Arup's '4See' macroeconomic embodied energy model. Richard Douthwaite from the Foundation

*Question and Answer session at the workshop.
Photograph courtesy of Dave Gibbons*

for the Economics of Sustainability (FEASTA) asked, "Why cap emissions if Peak Oil is coming anyway?".

The second day examined a series of highly successful local projects and approaches including Anna Hope's talk on the Ashley Vale self-build community in Bristol (see <http://www.ashleyvale.org.uk/home.htm>), Adam Twine's talk on the long genesis of the Westmill Co-operative's windfarm (see http://www.westmill.coop/westmill_home.asp) and Jerome Baddeley's talk on the progress of Meadows Community Energy Company in a relatively deprived area of Nottingham. Of generic interest were talks on innovating company structure for the purpose of optimising carbon reduction and a discussion of energy bonds as a mechanism for community finance of carbon reduction initiatives. The insights from these talks and the comments from a series of leading figures, such as Peter Harper from the Centre for Alternative Technology and Sue Riddlestone from BioRegional were discussed by the participants in break-out sessions. These were recorded along with the other outputs from the workshop, and are available at <http://transitiontolowcarbon.org/>.

Forthcoming Environmental Physics Group Events

Extreme Weather from Tornadoes to Hurricanes.

Ross Reynolds, Reading University will present at two locations:

University of Leeds: The Conference Auditorium, (joint with Yorkshire Branch) Wednesday 14th April, 2010 at 7:30pm

AND

University of Gloucestershire: TC103, Park Campus, Cheltenham (joint with South-West branch). Wednesday 19th May 2010. Refreshments from 7pm, starting 7.30pm.

Both of Ross's presentations will look at the origin, nature and prediction of severe weather in both the USA and UK, focusing on tornadic storms, hurricanes and explosive depressions. These phenomena have been and are still studied intensively, offering a significant challenge to researchers and operational meteorologists alike. For further information, contact John Sutcliffe at johnsutcliffe@googlemail.com (for Leeds event), and Ed Ratzler at secretary-sw@physics.org (South-West event).

***Combustion and NO_x in the Environment, East Midlands
Conference Centre, University of Nottingham
Wednesday 21st April 2010.***

A joint meeting organised by the Institute of Physics Combustion and Environmental Physics Groups. This meeting will be of interest to academics and industrialists alike and will bring together experts in combustion processes and the impacts of combustion products on human health and in the environment.

Nitrogen oxides are major pollutants from combustion and their emission is strictly regulated by law and technologically challenging to reduce. This meeting will focus on the fundamentals and practical aspects of low NO_x technologies.

Registration will be required for this meeting, and further information will be available from the Institute of Physics. Further details and the programme are available on the Environmental Physics Group web site under the '**Group calendar**' tab: <http://www.iop.org/activity/groups/subject/env/>

***The 1957 Windscale Fire (the west's worst nuclear accident)
University of Leeds: The Conference Auditorium,
Professor Richard Wakeford, University of Manchester.
Monday 26th April, 2010 at 7:30pm.***

Although it happened half a century ago, the nuclear reactor fire during October 1957 at Windscale Works, Sellafield, England, remains the largest accidental release of radioactive material into the environment that has occurred in the West. Extensive investigations into the causes and consequences of the Windscale accident have been carried out over the past fifty years, including a recent re-evaluation of the quantities of radionuclides released into the atmosphere and their subsequent travels over northern Europe. This presentation will provide a background to the accident, what happened during the fire, the environmental monitoring that took place.

***Extreme Weather from Tornadoes to Hurricanes.
University of Gloucestershire: TC103, Park Campus, Cheltenham
Wednesday 19th May 2010***

A talk by Ross Reynolds – see page 7 for details.

Environmental Physics Day

Phillips Room, Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London.

Wednesday 26th May 2010, from 1pm (followed by the AGM at 5.30pm and evening lecture at 6.30pm)

This year's Environmental Physics Day event will mark the 20th anniversary of the founding of the EPG. The day will see a mix of presentations from environmental physicists from a variety of disciplines including the EPG essay winners. It is a relaxed and friendly event to discuss environmental physics and find out more about the Group and its members. This year we have especially encouraged early career environmental physicists and founder members of the group to present research and likewise we encourage them to attend the meeting. **Travel grants** are available. The meeting will also incorporate the Group's AGM (see page 4) and will be followed by an evening lecture by Prof Sir Arnold Wolfendale (see page 10).

Among the topics that will be covered throughout the day are ocean optics, properties of dust aerosols and greenhouse gases.

The Members' Meeting commences at **1.00pm**, with lunch and a chance to meet other environmental physicists. The **AGM** will commence at **5:30pm** and the **evening lecture** by Professor Sir Arnold Wolfendale on 'Cosmic rays, climate and other matters' at **6.30pm**. The programme will be finalised shortly - please look on the website, www.iop.org/activity/groups/subject/env/ and click on 'Group Calendar' for updated information.

There will be **no charge** to Group members attending the meeting. Non-members will also be very welcome to attend (limited number of places available) subject to a registration fee of £10. The EPG will be allocating a number of **travel grants** for this meeting to assist with travel costs (apply to Peter Hodgson, at the address below).

To assist with catering, if you intend to come to the meeting, please return the form on the bottom of **page 16** stating **which events you plan to attend (Member's meeting or evening lecture or both) and your details** to: Dr. Peter Hodgson (see address at back of newsletter) or send an email with same details to: Peter.Hodgson@corusgroup.com.

***Environmental Physics Day Evening Lecture
Institute of Physics
Wednesday 26th May 2010, 6.30pm.***

After talks from members in the afternoon and the AGM, the EPG and the London and South East Branch will hold a joint evening lecture. For space and catering reasons, **please register** for this event by emailing Peter Hodgson – see reply slip for Environmental Physics Day on the bottom of **page 16**.

***Cosmic rays, climate and other matters
Prof Sir Arnold Wolfendale FRS, Physics Department, Durham University***

Cosmic rays provide one of the main sources of ionisation in the atmosphere and may have an effect on cloud formation and thereby atmospheric temperature. Furthermore, cosmic rays may have relevance to the well-known problem of lightning initiation, by way of the arrival of dense intensive air shower cores.

This evening lecture includes an examination of the 11-year cycle of cloud cover and radon, as well as nuclear bombs and the Chernobyl disaster. A Forbush decrease (a rapid decrease in the observed cosmic ray intensity following a coronal mass ejection) in the cosmic ray flux will also be studied, as well as the possibility of seeing ‘cigar shaped-clouds’ coming from air showers.

A brief mention will be made of the role of very high fluxes of high energy cosmic rays, and subsequent lightning events in the formation of life billions of years ago. Finally, the basic physics behind climate change is discussed.

More information about the speaker can be found on his webpage at: <http://www.dur.ac.uk/physics/staff/profiles/?username=dph6aww>

Optical Environmental Sensing VII
University of Southampton.
Monday 23rd – Friday 27th August 2010.

This meeting will be a session of the Photon10 conference, which will also include a plenary session on 'Green Photonics'. The meeting is intended as a forum for presentation and discussion of current developments in optical environmental sensing and is organised jointly by the IOP Optical and Environmental Physics Groups. The meeting will encompass a wide scope including new developments in optical measurement techniques and applications in monitoring the atmosphere, clouds and the terrestrial environment.

Photon10 will be held between 23rd - 27th August 2010 at the University of Southampton.

Further details are also available at: <http://www.photon.org.uk/activity/index.html>

Registration will required for this meeting. Further details will appear on the Environmental Physics Group web site under '**Group Calendar**'.

<http://www.iop.org/activity/groups/subject/env/>

Physics in the Animal World,
Institute of Physics, Portland Place, London.
Wednesday 24th November 2010, 2pm.

An open meeting (including non-members and the general public) discussing the physics behind the animal world, including:

- What physics is behind the flapping of wings?
- What causes iridescence in animals?
- How do diseases spread in populations?
- Can insects orientate their flight direction using environmental cues?

Posters on physics and the animal world welcome. Please register posters for the event or register your attendance by emailing Curtis Wood at curtis@physics.org

Forthcoming IOP Events

Novel Aspects of Surfaces and Materials (NASM3), Chancellors Hotel and Conference Centre, Manchester.

Sunday 11th – Thursday 15th April 2010

Organised by the Applied Physics Technology Division of the Institute of Physics

This conference is the third in the series and will include presentations on current applied physics challenges, developments and approaches to surfaces and materials. Speakers will share their vision and knowledge on contemporary research and technology. Interdisciplinary and interactive, the conference will highlight new developments in the field and promote opportunities for new collaborations on funding applications and networking. For further details, see <http://nasm.iop.org/>

Other Activities and news

Research Student Conference Fund

Supporting research students

Research Student Conference Fund

Providing financial support to research student members, to attend international conferences and major national meetings.

Apply for up to £250 during the course of your PhD.

Applications are considered on a quarterly basis and should reach the Institute by: 1 March, 1 June, 1 September or 1 December

For further information see www.iop.org or contact supportandgrants@iop.org

IOP Institute of Physics

IOP Briefing Notes

In December 2009, the Institute of Physics launched *IOP Briefing Notes* on topical physics-related issues, the first covering physics and climate change. See http://www.iop.org/News/file_38336.pdf Briefing notes provide an overview of the topic and how it relates to physics.

If you would like to join the climate change debate, there is an IOP forum on climate change. Log on to <http://my.iop.org> for more details. If you have forgotten your password, click the 'Forgotten your login details' link or contact member.services@iop.org

IOPscience

Available from March, IOPscience is a new platform for IOP-hosted journals that makes it easier for researchers to discover the relevant content of journals and manage their research information. Take a tour and find out more at <http://iopscience.iop.org>

EPG Committee

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This newsletter is also available on the web and in larger print sizes

The contents of this newsletter do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the Institute of Physics, except where explicitly stated.

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I intend to come to the Environmental Physics Group **Environmental Physics Day** and/or **evening lecture** at the Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London, **Wednesday 26th May 2010**. Please post to Peter Hodgson, or email him the details at peter.hodgson@corusgroup.com

Afternoon Member's Meeting Evening lecture Both (please tick)

Name: -----

Address: -----

Tel.: ----- Email: -----